

Invoice

Bill To:

Dr. Ramírez-Estudillo Abel

Invoice No: ICMCRJ-3-1543**Invoice Date:** 17-09-2024**Due Date:** 19-09-2024

Department of Retina and Vitreous, Fundación Hospital
Nuestra Señora de la Luz I.A.P. Mexico City, Mexico

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	Quantity	Unit price	Amount
Multimodal Fundus Imaging of Outer Retinal Tubulations after Ranibizumab Injections in Choroidal Osteoma	1	\$.1000 USD	\$ 1000 USD
Service Tax(18%)	1	\$ 180 USD	\$ 180 USD

Total APC: \$ 1180 USD**Company Registration Number:** U92140TG2022PTC163407**Company Website:** <https://salientvisionarypub.com/>

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